

MANGALIK DOSHA – PROS AND CONS

A. Sundara Rajan* & Dr. K. Jothimani**

* Research Scholar, School of Vedic Astrology, Vels Institute of Science, Technology and Advanced Studies (VISTAS), Pallavaram, Chennai, Tamilnadu

** Supervisor, School of Vedic Astrology, Vels Institute of Science, Technology and Advanced Studies (VISTAS), Pallavaram, Chennai, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

There are different reasons why many people have delayed marriages and one of the astrological reason is fear of Mangalik Dosha. Manglik Dosha holds great significance in astrology. Manglik Dosha is directly tied to marriage in Hinduism. Here the researcher tried to light up the reason for the Mangalik Dosha and its effects.

Key Words: Marriage, Mars, Venus, Male, Female, Harmony, Delay, Denial, Mangalik, Guja, Dosha

Introduction:

During wedding preparations, we might have come across the term Manglik with reference to the matching of the prospective bride and groom's horoscopes and you might have wondered what it is all about and what connection does it have with marriage. Manglik Dosh holds great significance in astrology. In Hinduism, Manglik Dosha is directly linked to marriage. When we do match making, we become afraid when the astrologer tells us that our child is a Manglik and fear is installed in the minds of the parents especially for the girls'.

The planet Mars seems to be especially harsh on girls and their proposals are either discarded or selected with utmost care. There is also a lot of confusion as who is a manglik. Some astrologers take its position from lagna and some from lagna, moon and venus. This makes 80 to 90 percent people Manglik and Astrologers charge heavy amounts for remedies.

The planet mars rules blood in our bodies. Scientifically, if the Rh factor of the bride and bridegroom are same then during childbirth, some medicines are prescribed for the girl. In earlier times, people noticed the same and avoided such proposals.

It is said in astrology that if Mars is in the 1st, 2nd, 4th, 7th, 8th and 12th position in a person's horoscope, then the person is considered to be suffering from Manglik Dosha. Manglik Dosha occurs due to the position of planet Mars. Talking about Mars, it is called the God of war and this planet remains unmarried. Strangely, the planet which is itself unmarried creates such combinations in the horoscope of the native that constant problems remain in not just marriage proposals but also married life. Therefore it is generally advised that a Manglik person should get married to a Manglik or else there will be a bad effect on married life.

History of Mangal Graha:

Mars, the Red planet is fiery and masculine. According to Hindu mythology, he is the son of Bhumi (Earth) and Varaha (Boar). When Earth was lying submerged under the cosmic ocean, stolen by the demon Hiranyaksha, Vishnu in his incarnation as Varaha brought it out on his tusks and placed it in orbit. He embraced Bhoomi Devi and gifted her red coral as a token of their courtship. But Bhoomi Devi dropped the coral into the ocean. From the coral emerged a beautiful red child who got the name Lohitanga, which translates into red-limbed body. The child is also called Bhooma, meaning Bhoomi's son.

The Earth desired her son to be vitreous. She went to Sage Bhardwaja and narrated the story of birth of this child. She asked the meritorious Sage Bhardwaj to take the child in his guidance and preach him. Sage Bhardwaj accepted the child. He named him Bhauma which means the son of Earth. Bhauma came to known as the son of son of Sage Bharadwaj and Goddess Prithvi (Earth). He received learning from his father.

The child was nurtured by the sage Bharadwaj, one of the Sapta Rishis, in his hermitage near the Narmada. After hearing of his origin from the sage, the child went to the forest and did penance for a long time. Pleased with his devotion, Brahma accorded him the position of a planet in the celestial sky.

The role of Mars in astrology is of great significance because it often interferes with the marriage of a native due to Mangal Dosha. Mars in ancient mythology is often considered as lohit (red), angry faced. It is also called the god of rage and celibate (unmarried). However, it is also responsible for courage and determination. People under the radar of this planet are often high tempered and have rage in their heart. Every planet will affect a person in both positive and negative ways and this holds good for Mars also. A strong Mars in horoscope indicates favourable scenarios for a native. The Mars in flourishing mode will give youthful energy, power and courage to compete in life and bestows a person with good management skill. However, a weak or malefic Mars may dampen the thinking power of a person by making him full of rage, anger and aggression. This may create hurdles in a native's life and the person may sometimes press the self-destruction button.

Once upon a time, a very strong rakshasa called Andhaka performed a hard penance to please Lord Shiva. Lord Shiva was pleased, and offered him a boon of his choice. Andhkarsura asked for a boon that everytime a drop of his blood fell on the earth, he wanted a new Andhkarsura created. Lord Shiva granted him the boon.

Armed by this powerful boon, Andhkasura started a reign of terror. Nobody could defeat him, as every successful attack that wounded him caused his blood to drop onto the ground. Every time his blood touched the ground, it ended up creating an army of Andhakasuras. This army of Andhakasuras were very difficult to defeat. They spread destruction everywhere around, fought with kings and devas alike, and were impossible to defeat. Everyone went to Lord Shiva, and asked him to protect them.

Lord Shiva battled with Andhakasura, but every time Andhaka's blood touched the ground, a new Andhakasura was created. After fighting for a long time, Lord Shiva got tired. Drops of his sweat fell on earth. At the place where they fell, the earth opened up. From the womb of earth, Lord Mangal came out. Mangaldev started absorbing every drop of blood of Andhkasura that fell out. Thus, Lord Mangal assisted Lord Shiva in the battle, and prevented Andhakasura from being reborn by using his special boon. Assisted by an able Mangaldev, Lord Shiva won the battle easily against Andhkasura and killed him. Since Mangaldev was thus the child of Lord Shiv and Prithvi (Bhumi, the Planet Earth), Mangaldev is also called Bhaum.

Mangal Dosh Meaning:

Mars has a special place in astrology. According to astrology, Mars is the commander of the planets. They are considered to be the causative planets of courage, energy, brotherhood, relationships, land, power, and valor. When these are present in the horoscope of a person, then there is Mangal Dosh on him. According to astrology, when Mars is in a strong position in a person's horoscope. Then that person gets might, happiness and wealth. Due to this, relations with younger siblings get better, and the relationship gets strong. But according to the beliefs, there is a lack of harmony between husband and wife due to the defect of Mars in the horoscope.

According to beliefs, the most negative effect of Mangal Dosh is on marriage and married life. Due to Mangal dosh, there are obstructions in marriage, there is a dispute in married life. There is a possibility of legal trouble, debt problem, and serious injury. Some remedies have been mentioned in astrology to reduce their effect and to make Mars auspicious.

According to astrology, if Mars is situated in the Lagna or ascendant, second house, fourth house, seventh house, eighth house, or twelfth house of any person's horoscope. Such a situation created in the horoscope is considered to be Mangal Dosh.

Effects of Mangal Dosh:

When Mars is Situated in the 1st House:

The 1st house represents the house of spouse. Thus it normally affects the married life leading to unnecessary conflicts. It might also lead to physical assault and violence. Due to such unacceptable behavior such a person might suffer from tension, distress, separation or even divorce.

Mars in 1st House natives will always want to run the extra mile to make their dreams come true and to show the world what they're capable of. Because they are very confident, people will always be impressed by their actions and behavior. People with Mars in the 1st House react almost immediately to any type of situation and can be pressing with their endless energy or imaginative ways.

It's normal for these natives to start more than one projects at a time and to not be able to follow their plans through. They're usually reckless, confident and not at all considerate of other people's feelings. There's no one more independent than them, and when talking, they're usually telling the truth in the bluntest way. It's important for them to be spontaneous, but the fact that they don't think before taking action can get them in trouble. Whether being conscious or not about it, they can initiate conflicts when bored. Mars is the ruler of Aries and the planet of aggressiveness, self-confidence and war. Enthusiastic when having to do something new, they soon lose their interest and hurry to see what the next adventure can bring them.

When Mars is Situated in the 2nd House:

A person's family life is affected. It also creates obstacles in the married life and the professional life. When Mars is placed in the 2nd house, the natives are likely to be sensitive. They may get flared up over small issues and pick up quarrels with others. Besides, the natives may have difficulties in pronouncing some words. If Mars is afflicted, then the natives even suffer from speech-related issues. The second house is the house of wealth, speech, initial education and family.

Mars in the 2nd House gives you an attitude to accumulate wealth and possessions by hook or by crook. This position of Mars has Mangal dosh and is bad for family harmony and will affect the longevity of marriage. It suggests separation from spouse and second marriage. It will also make you susceptible to eye diseases, injury, toothache, and accidents.

The native will also exhibit high zeal and harsh speech, besides difficulty in uttering words. He/she will make friends easily with malicious and evil-minded people, who will distract you and create a blockage in your logical mind. However, good lordships will bring success through enterprise, legacies and inheritance.

In the field of education, Mars positioned in the 2nd house means breaks, delays and constant change. Mars being a natural malefic planet will entangle the native in the search for desirable earnings. He/she will not receive due rewards and return for his/her efforts. They may experience frequent disputes in domestic life due to their aggression and high expectations from others. They will face difficulty in having a child; and sometimes, with this placement, the birth of a child brings loss of job or destruction of business. A negative Mars in the 2nd house makes a native aggressive and triggers your anger to pick up fights with family members and loved ones. He/she will be deprived of their love and warmth as you will be cunning towards them. He/she will also struggle in accumulating wealth as Mars is your outer personality, which will reflect as greediness towards materialistic gain.

When Mars is Situated in the 4th House:

4th house is the most important house in astrology as it is about your happiness, mother, luxury, and tangible assets. Mars is the planet that provokes and tests your limits to the extent you can control your temper. This will have adverse effects at the professional front. Such a person will switch jobs and also will not be successful professionally. Financial trouble will keep lurking.

It is the planet of bully so this position of Mars in the 4th house makes you undergo quarrels with your mother, relatives and friends because of your egoistic behaviour and inadequate understanding. You will be owning houses but will never be happy and satisfied. This position will instigate greediness and you will always resonate from the space of lack. There will be no peace of mind, but your positive approach and determination will help you to overcome all hindrances.

Mars in the 4th house will also make you creative, enthusiastic and charming, which will attract the opposite sex. You will be concerned about domestic affairs and ongoing ups and downs. You will forgive others easily and never dwell in the past. You tend to develop unwanted desires, being short-tempered and because of a lack of sufficient knowledge. You do not adapt to the situation and become furious if you are in an uncomfortable zone.

4th house is a kendra house where natural malefic Mars is posited. This means you will undergo struggles from birth till the age of 25. This might create difficulty in your birthing process; parents will suffer from limited resources and earnings. You will also face uncomfortable situations due to quarrelsome parents and malnutrition. This position of Mars will also bring breaks and delays in your education and career.

Mars or Mangal being primary significator for the immovable asset and its placement in fourth house gives landed properties along with disputes, Mars here also blesses native with conveyances, vehicles and such comforts. Person will own houses but will not be happy over there.

As being delicate and sensitive house, presence of Mars in 4th house is not welcomed, maybe it can give material pleasures but on the other hand it is not considered good for mother, mental peace & happiness i.e. internal bliss which ultimate goal of every species.

When Mars is Situated in the 7th House:

Such a person has too much of energy and will be ill-tempered resulting in not being able to maintain cordial relationship with family members. Also this person will be very dominating and dictating over his or her partner and s/he might also have many partners.

As Mars is a planet with much power, energy, courage and bravery, when it occupies the 7th house, brings enormous aggression and strength in the native. If you are a person with Mars in 7th house then, you will always try to hold the upper hand in all the cases. Because of your short temperament, most of the time you will get involved in a discussion, that will be turned into a hot argument. Mars is vitality, energy and totally unpredictable. It's impossible to make him changed against his wish. It will make you very much independent and courageous. You will not be afraid to face the challenges of life. You will have decision making power. You will be able to fight with all kinds of opposition. If this Mars is in Own sign or Exalted, it will give you lot of Confidence. But a person with Mars in 7th will be straight forward. If there is no other Affliction, He will be honest and Protective. If a Benefic Mars is placed in the 7th house from Lagna it can make you a Businessman specially in Business like Real estate, Land, Engineering etc.

Mars occupying the 7th house makes you manglik. Here, Mars causes obstacles and delay in marriage. It may also spoil the married life by creating misunderstanding between you and your spouse. The opinion of husband and wife generally does not match. There are many factor behind it but Ego problem is considered as one of the vital factor among them. So it is always advised that a Manglik boy should marry a Manglik girl or vice versa to get rid of the destructive effects caused by Mars.

As 7th house also signifies professional relationship, an afflicted Mars may give disturbance in the relations among business partners. Yet if you try hard and work restlessly, even if there is Mars in your 7th house, it will yield good results in the field of marketing, salesmanship etc.

Mars is a separative Planet. So its influence in the house of Marriage is not considered Auspicious. When Mars Occupies the 7th house it may make you sexually energetic and bold. At the same time it may make you restless and even harsh that will have an inauspicious effect on your married life. If Mars is also in the 7th house of Navamsa, Fights and Friction will be regular thing in Married Life. It creates lot of frustration in

Marriage. So, it's quite easy to understand that the married life is not going to be so good Unless Mars is not Yogkaraka or in Own sign or exalted. The native will be the aggressive one who will not willing to compromise at all. The influence of Mars on the 7th house of Navamsa or D9 chart is more problematic than D1 chart.

When Mars is in the 8th House:

Mars in 8th House people are energetic, lustful and enthusiastic to know as many things as possible, to understand how people work and to know their secrets. They may have some problems with money, so a partner who can help them be more financially stable would be their true hero because they'd no longer stress that much about surviving. That's why it's possible for these natives to marry out of interest.

8th house is the house of transformations, death like experiences, sudden losses, sudden gains, secrets, mystery, obstacles, health, longevity and so on. Natives having Mars in 8th house have a strong desire to get to the depth of things, expose secrets and play detective. The person is also likely to face financial issues due to partner, who may be overly extravagant leading to troubles. People under the influence of Mars in 8th house like to see how people react to certain situations.

Mars' position here also increases the possibility of sudden death. Such a fatality could be caused by a serious injury. This position indicates a lot of problems with business partner or life partner on account of mismanagement of money, especially if malefic influence is there.

They usually want revenge when a person crosses them, being capable to hold grudges for a lifetime. If someone just says something wrong, they see it as a huge betrayal and no one can ever change their mind. It's difficult for them to trust others, but they surely do it more intensely than others.

When Mars is Situated in the 12th House:

Life could be a little unfortunate towards people with Mars in 12th house. There would be a lot of strange happenings. You may encounter losses through secret enemies. Moreover, you have intense emotions, which often become the root cause of all your troubles. You have a lot of regrets and bitterness inside, which needs to be controlled. People take advantage of this weakness. You strongly need to control your impulse. If you rely on your emotions than reason, the repercussions are likely to be against your welfare.

A bad Mars could also cause false imprisonment and accusations to the native. You should try to avoid situations where arguments or confrontation is required. The combination of external situations and internal emotions makes the person feel stifled at times. Such natives should learn to use their energy in a constructive way. They should make it a habit to release their pent-up emotions and make it a practice to forgive and forget. The sense of isolation in life makes you a fit for professions where you could work behind the scenes.

The natives with Mars in the 12th house will have a mixed love life with ups and down in it. The natives will be extremely loving and caring towards their spouses. But they will lack the sexual tension in their life. This gives them a hard time in life. To solve it, you need the help of a love marriage astrologer to overcome this problem. Other than that, the natives will be great to their partners and their loved ones.

Mars in the 12th house gives the natives a hard time in marriage. As per married predictions by date of birth in astrology, the 12th house gives them a partner with supportive nature but still, they will lack the attraction and sexual need in life. And this will create a great problem in their life and their partner may not be satisfied and happy with you in life. To make this marriage work you need to work hard to understand your partner and make this relationship work in life.

Mars and Venus:

Mars is the planet of lust, sexuality, high passions and war. Male or female, your wild side is a gift of Mars, while Venus bestows romantic love and beauty and happily-ever-after. That said, I guess I don't have to tell you that while both planets greatly impact your love life, they do so with vastly different energies and consequences. Astrology can give you a leg up on seeing beyond the bliss of great sex, to the bottom line of whatever it is you really want in the game of love.

While Mars is masculine and Venus is feminine in the classic sense, we each embody both male and female characteristics. Your X-rated fantasies and behavior, your sexual arousal and needs, even your style of lovemaking are in Mars's wheelhouse. Your romantic, love-and-devotion dreams are the bailiwick of Venus. For example: If Mars rules your chart, fidelity probably won't be high on your priority list, but world-class sex may be. If Venus rules, then romance, home and hearth are probably among your priorities. The right balance can lead to a happy and long-term love life.

While Mars and Venus aren't the only pieces in the love puzzle, understanding their potent love/lust energies can give you a leg up on figuring out where the comfortable compatibilities lie between you and your significant other, and where the obvious bred-in-the-bone conflicts are accidents waiting to happen. To find out where your Mars and Venus are in your chart and what energetic patterns they're generating, you'll need a compatibility chart done by a professional astrologer.

How Mangalik Dosh Arised?

We treat the disease caused by the water (Moon is the ruler for water) as a JalaDosham. Whereas we are damaging the marital life by saying that the change in the body caused by Mars is Mangalik Dosh. Those

who dominate by Mars who is the Ruler(Karagan) of blood will be slightly more emotional than the others. It can be a feeling of anger for some, a feeling of speed for some and a feeling of lust for some.

Those who dominate Mars will have a greater inclination towards marriage and relationship. Those who dominated by Mars are said to be Mangalik people. But those who are Non Mangalik will get divorced over time as they will not show much interest in sexual relationship. For those who are Mangalik marrying those who are Non-Mangalik will cause marital problems between them. Indicatively Mangalik would be more sexual inclination but and Non-Mangalik would deny it. That is the reason, it is recommended that Mangalik should marry a Mangalik only.

At one point of time, the Non-Mangalik will jokingly tells to go somewhere else if you need / want for relationship. So the Mangalik will look for another mate considering it as permission. No harm will come to the parent or In-laws due to Mangalik Dosh. For bed comforts and sexual happiness only, it is advised that either both should be Mangalik or Non-Mangalik so that it is balance their interest.

Exploring how Mars Dosh came to be, it seems that Mars and Venus placement, aspect and conjunction, affliction in the Natural Zodiac (Horoscope of Kalapursh) creating Mangalik Dosh. Aries is said to be Lagna (Ascendant) in term of Natural Zodiac. And Aries and its ruler Mars denotes male and the opposite house Libra and its ruler Venus termed as Female i.e the opposite sex.

It is said to be Mangalik Dosh if Mars is placed in 1st, 2nd, 4th, 7th, 8th and 12th houses from Lagna (Ascendant). Let's explore this according to the Kalapursha horoscope for a while.

If Mars is placed in 1st house i.e Aries, it will have 7th aspect with Libra i.e house of Venus. If Mars is placed in the Second house i.e Taurus the house of Venus, then there will be aspect of Mars and Venus. And the second house Taurus Venus is associated with the term masculine sign Aries. The fourth house is Cancer (Katakam), the house where Jupiter's exaltation while the house where Mars is getting debilitate. If Mars is placed in the debilitate house and watery sigh, it will affect the masculinity of the male. The seventh house is Libra, the house of Venus. Venus aspect occurs even if Mars stands here

Next is Scorpio, the eighth house for Natural Zodiac (Kalapurusha). If Mars is placed in Scorpio, it will aspect Taurus in seventh aspect so this also causes the Mars-Venus conjunction. And the Eighth House is a place of secret and sexual organs.

Next is Pisces, which is the twelfth house for Natural Zodiac (Kalapurush). This is the ruling house of the Guru. And Venus is getting exalted. If Mars is here the horoscope will be waved between devotion and bed. Therefore, in a horoscope, the combination of Mars and Venus without the Jupiter's aspect will cause more lustfuland affect masculinity as it is watery sign.

It is with this in mind that it appears that in the absence of a medical facility a couple may have developed a restriction called Mars Dosh in consideration of social security so as not to be affected by excessive marital bliss or unsatisfactory masculinity. This Mars-Venus conjunction can be visually seen in the horoscopes of a husband / wife who is not satisfied with the comfort of the bed.

Is there any exemption for Mangalik Dosh?

Considering the delay of marriage, it is believed by few astrologers that the following are the exemptions for Mangalik and in this situations the Dosh is getting nullified.

- The Mangal Dosh gets cancelled if the other partner has the Saturn posited in the 1st, 4th, 7th, 8th and 12th respectively.
- The Mangal Dosh gets cancelled when the planet Mars is weak or debilitated, combust and aspected by benefic planets.
- The Mangal Dosh will get cancelled if the planet Jupiter is posited in the Kendra or Trikon in a female horoscope. The native will be fortunate enough, intelligent and will be blessed with son.
- The Mangal dosh also gets cancelled when It is posited in movable sign such as Aries, Cancer, Libra and Capricorn.
- The Manglik gets cancelled if the planet Mars is posited in the 4th house in its own sign or in the sign of Venus.
- The Magal Dosh gets cancelled when the planet Mars is in conjunction with Rahu, or Moon and Venus are posited in the 2nd house, if planet Rahu is posited in the Kendra and when Mars gets aspect from Jupiter.
- The Kuja Dosh gets cancelled if the numbers of inauspicious planets are posited in the 1st house, 4th house, 7th house, 8th house and 12th house in a male chart than a female chart.
- If Mars is placed in the ascendant in Aries, Leo or Aquarius sign, the bad effects of Mangal Dosha will be cancelled.
- Mars posited in 2nd house in either Gemini or Virgo sign will cancel the Dosha.
- Presence of Mars in the 4th house in either Aries or Scorpio sign will save you from the harsh treatment of Mangal Dosha.
- Mangal Dosha will be cancelled with Mars present in the 7th house in Cancer or Capricorn sign.

- If Mars is posited in the 8th house in Sagittarius or Pisces sign, you are free from Mangal Dosha.
- Mars present in the 12th house in either Taurus or Libra sign will eliminate the possible effects of Mangal Dosha.
- If Mars is placed in the movable signs like Aries, Cancer, Libra, and Capricorn, then Mangal Dosha exists no more.
- If planets like Venus and Moon are placed in 2nd house of the horoscope, Mangal Dosha is cancelled.
- The conjunction of Jupiter and Venus in either ascendant or 7th house cancels Mangal Dosha.
- The Mangal Dosh gets cancelled when the planet Moon is in Kendra.

All of these exceptions are self-deception. In fact, there is no exception to Mangalik Dosha except getting married the same level of Mangalik since it is a matter of blood factor RH+ and RH, which are the components of the blood, so getting married in the same level of Mangalik will reduce the problem.

For example, if the male horoscope has Mars in the 1st, 7th, 8th house from Lagna (Ascendant), it is better for the woman to have Mars in the same place as Mars, as well as in the 2nd, 4th, 12th house of Mars with the same system of marriage. No matter how many remedies are made, marriages made with such a connection will be better.

Conclusion:

Let no one need to be afraid for Mangalik Dosha. More than half of the human in the earth with Mangalik Dosha. Mangalik Dosha is not the reason for the wedding delay. So it is better to know the nature of Mangalik Dosha through a good astrologer and act accordingly.

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